

Multilevel Electricity Trading Simulation considering Energy Communities Participation

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Abstract—The EU is encouraging the creation of local energy communities (LECs) for electricity trading, promoting local balance and a self-sustained community while reducing electricity bills. Local electricity markets (LEMs) ease the electricity trading of distributed energy resources while incentivizing the integration of renewable energy sources into the grid. However, presently, LEMs have low liquidity, and the demand is significantly higher than the supply. One possible solution to address this issue is participation in the wholesale market, assessing lower prices, and providing additional savings. This work proposes a multilevel electricity trading framework for LECs' participation. The simulation framework comprises different LEM models for electricity trading at different levels, culminating in wholesale market participation through a LEC aggregator. Results show the benefits of LECs' participation in the multilevel trading platform with significant savings.

Index Terms—Electricity Markets, Local Energy Communities, Multilevel Electricity Trading, Renewable Generation

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of renewable energy sources (RES) is rising in the European Union (EU) resulting from environmental and climatic concerns and goals [1]. By 2030, the EU expects to increase energy efficiency to at least 32.5%, increase the share of renewable energy consumption to at least 32%, and reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by at least 40% from 1990 levels [2]. Moreover, the EU is aiming to achieve a net-zero economy and climate neutrality by 2050 [3]. To accomplish these goals, the European Parliament and the Council of the EU published Directive (EU) 2019/944 on June 2019, establishing “common rules of the internal market for electricity” [4]. The directive brings significant changes to the markets and business models for electricity, giving real alternatives to the end users of energy, enhancing their empowerment, opening new business opportunities while maintaining higher service standards, and promoting sustainability and supply security.

EU's directive also encourages the creation of local energy communities (LEC) for trading electricity at the neighborhood level using RES-based generation and information and communication technology (ICT) [4]. By selling their surplus

electricity generated by the RES, consumers (or prosumers) and support local balance while reducing the electricity bill costs. This incentivization investment that supports a self-sustained community creating new opportunities, and challenges, for LEC participants. For instance, the operation of electricity markets (EMs) is significantly impacted by the intermittent nature of RES and their extensive integration, which imposes new constraints on the sector [5]. EMs are constantly adapting to new realities and due to the growing number of business models and actors involved, their behavior becomes more unpredictable and complex.

Local electricity markets (LEMs) are a new approach to electricity trading, allowing EMs decentralization. LEMs facilitate the electricity trading between distributed energy resources (DERs) and increase the integration of RES into the grid, reducing the need for traditional fossil-fueled power plants [6]. Currently LEMs have low liquidity, and the demand is higher than the supply. Wholesale market participation is a possible solution to address this issue. Represented by aggregators, LECs can participate in wholesale markets, accessing lower prices and providing consumers additional savings [7].

In this context, this work proposes a multilevel electricity trading framework from LECs to wholesale EM. The study considers ten LECs with local RES-based generation. Each LEC runs its internal community trading attempting to satisfy the local demand. We consider different LECs using distinct trading mechanisms. Such mechanisms are based on double auction-based markets and LEC transactions with centralized optimization. After the local transactions have been set, LECs trade electricity among each other to sell their surplus or buy faulty demand. For this, a double auction is performed by an aggregator of the LECs, which will participate in the wholesale EM with the remaining demand or supply.

After this introductory section, section II presents the proposed simulation framework. Section III details the case study scenario, describing the different LECs, to demonstrate the multilevel electricity trading in the proposed framework. Section IV analyses and discusses the simulation results. And section V outlines the conclusions and perspectives of future work.

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II. PROPOSED SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

This work proposes a multilevel simulation framework for electricity trading leveraging LECs. The proposed framework comprises three negotiation levels, as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Multilevel electricity trading simulation framework

The first trading level (Lv1) represents the typical LEMs where each LEC trades electricity among its prosumers and consumers. At this level, two trading models are available for simulation. One option is to use a LEM model with centralized optimization (subsection A), where the LEC aggregator runs an optimization model to improve the community's energy efficiency while reducing its customers' electricity bills. The other possibility is a double auction-based model with strategic bidding (subsection II.B). In this case, each player runs an optimization model before bidding in the LEM.

Using the unsatisfied demand/supply of Lv1, in the second trading level (Lv2), the aggregator runs a double auction-based market [8] to trade electricity between aggregated LECs, aiming to avoid the consumers' need to buy electricity from the grid at a higher price. On the other hand, prosumers try to sell their surplus at higher prices than the feed-in tariff. Finally, in the third negotiation level (Lv3), the aggregator participates in the wholesale day-ahead market with the unsatisfied demand/supply of each hourly period of Lv2, trying to buy or sell electricity at the best possible price. However, to participate in the wholesale, the aggregator must ensure a minimum of 1 MWh per period. In the hours with demand/surplus lower than 1 MWh, he will not be able to participate, and his aggregators will have to buy/sell from/to the grid. For the wholesale market simulation, the Iberian market day-ahead model [9] is considered.

A. LEM model with centralized optimization

The LEM model with centralized optimization considers a community-based market where each player can buy or sell electricity in a LEM or from a backup system. A MILP mathematical model is used to optimize the operational costs of the LEC. Eq. (1) presents the total operational costs.

$$\min_{E_{t,i}^{\text{buy}}, E_{t,i}^{\text{sell}}} C^{\text{LEC}} = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} (E_{t,i}^{\text{buy}} \times \pi_{t,i}^{\text{buy}} - E_{t,i}^{\text{sell}} \times \pi_{t,i}^{\text{sell}}) \times \Delta t + c^{\text{fix}} \quad (1)$$

where, $E_{t,i}^{\text{buy}}$ represents the electricity bought outside the LEC, $\pi_{t,i}^{\text{buy}}$ is the price of electricity bought outside of the LEC, $E_{t,i}^{\text{sell}}$ represents the electricity sold outside the LEC, $\pi_{t,i}^{\text{sell}}$ is the price of electricity sold outside of the LEC, Δt is the hour adjust parameter and c^{fix} represents the fixed costs paid by each player. Eq. (2) presents the energy balance for each player.

$$\begin{aligned} E_{t,i}^{\text{buy}} + E_{t,i}^{\text{genPV}} + E_{t,i}^{\text{dch}} + E_{t,i}^{\text{EV dch}} + E_{t,i}^{\text{buy LEC}} &= \\ = E_{t,i}^{\text{sell}} + E_{t,i}^{\text{load}} + E_{t,i}^{\text{ch}} + E_{t,i}^{\text{EV ch}} + E_{t,i}^{\text{sell LEC}} & \\ \forall t \in N_t, \forall i \in N_i & \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where, $E_{t,i}^{\text{genPV}}$ represents the energy generated, $E_{t,i}^{\text{dch}}$ is the energy discharged of battery, $E_{t,i}^{\text{EV dch}}$ represents the energy discharged of EV, $E_{t,i}^{\text{buy LEC}}$ represents the energy bought from other members of the LEC, $E_{t,i}^{\text{load}}$ represents the load, $E_{t,i}^{\text{ch}}$ is the energy charge of battery, $E_{t,i}^{\text{EV ch}}$ represents the energy charged by EV, and $E_{t,i}^{\text{sell LEC}}$ represents the energy sold to the others LEC members. Eq. (3) presents the local market balance.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_i} E_{t,i}^{\text{buy LEC}} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} E_{t,i}^{\text{sell LEC}}, \forall t \in N_t \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) ensures the perfect match between energy bought and sold inside of the LEC. The model is subject to other restrictions namely, maximum and minimum for buying and selling energy, only one action is possible to do at the same time, energy balance for battery and EV battery and also only one of the charge or discharge actions is possible to perform at the same time. The model is implemented in python environment using the mipy library [10] with CBC free solver.

B. Double auction-based model with strategic bidding

The double auction-based model with strategic bidding considers a LEM in which consumers, prosumers equipped with PV, and CHP producers transact energy to minimize costs and maximize incomes. Details of such competitive market can be found in [11]. To simulate strategic bidding, a metaheuristic, vortex search (VS) algorithm, is implemented to solve a bi-level optimization problem in which consumers search for the minimization of costs and producers for the maximization of incomes at the upper level:

$$\min_{s_{i,t}, d_{i,t}} C_i = \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\sum_j c p_t \cdot x_{j,i,t} + c_t^{\text{grid}} \cdot E_{i,t}^{\text{buy}} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\max_{s_{j,t}, g_{j,t}} I_n = \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\sum_i c p_t \cdot x_{j,i,t} + c_t^{\text{F}} \cdot E_{j,t,s}^{\text{sell}} - C_{j,t}^{\text{total}} \right) \quad (5)$$

Eq. (4) and (5) model the upper-level problem (a multi-follower problem), where the tuples $(s_{i,t}, d_{i,t})$ and $(s_{j,t}, g_{j,t})$ include the consumer price bid $s_{i,t}$ for the amount of energy $d_{i,t}$, and the price offer $s_{j,t}$ for the amount of energy $g_{j,t}$ at time t respectively. $x_{j,i,t}$ is the energy bought in the LEM by agent i from agent j (kWh); $E_{i,t}^{\text{buy}}$ is the energy bought from the grid by agent i (kWh); $x_{j,i,t}$ is the energy sold by agent j to agent i (kWh); $E_{j,t,s}^{\text{sell}}$ is the energy sold (kWh) to the grid by agent j (we assume that only PV generation can be injected into the grid); and $C_{j,t}^{\text{total}}$ is production cost of local generation. Such cost $C_{j,t}^{\text{total}}$ is assumed to be 0 for PV generation and $2 \cdot b_{\text{CHP}} \cdot \sqrt{G_{j,t}}$ for the CHPs, with b_{CHP} as a cost factor, and $G_{j,t}$ as the produced energy. Consumer and producer costs and incomes are subject to $c p_t$, which is the LEM clearing price (EUR/kW) that is bounded by the grid tariff (c_t^{grid}) and the feed-in tariff (c_t^{F}).

The lower level problem (single leader) is modelled as a symmetric pool-based market, where first, supply and demand curves are obtained by the sets GE (with the offers of energy $(s_{j,t}, g_{j,t})$ in ordered in ascending price order) and DE (with the bids for energy $(s_{i,t}, d_{i,t})$ in descending price order) respectively. With those sets, a linear problem is formulated as [12]:

$$\max_{d_i^*, g_j^*} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \lambda_i^d \cdot d_i^* - \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \lambda_j^g \cdot g_j^* \quad (6a)$$

st.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_c} d_i^* - \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} g_j^* = 0 \quad : cp_t (\text{dual variable}) \quad (6b)$$

$$0 \leq d_i^* \leq DE_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_c \quad (6c)$$

$$0 \leq g_j^* \leq GE_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, N_p \quad (6d)$$

where d_i^* and g_j^* are the demand and supply bids ordered by price (i.e., belonging to sets DE_i and GE_j), and λ_i^d and λ_j^g are the corresponding bid prices. Thus, Eq. (6a) maximizes the social welfare of market participants; Eq. (6b) is the balance constraint, and its dual variable is the clearing price cp_t ; Eq. (6c) and (6d) guarantee the generation and consumption limits. After solving this linear problem, a reverse procedure is used to determine the LEM transactions $x_{i,j}$ and $x_{j,i}$ from the accepted bids d_i^* and g_j^* . In addition, network constraints are also considered using a power flow analysis executed in MATPOWER.

Figure 2 illustrates the model's iterative process in which, in a first step, a set of bids are generated according to the search procedure of VS.

Figure 2. Market participants and interactions in the LEM

After the market clearing procedure is employed to determine the clearing price and power flow validation is done considering energy transactions. Those values are combined in a fitness function to determine the performance of the solution. New bids are then generated in the neighborhood of the initial solution (see VS procedure for more details) and evaluated with the same procedure. The initial solution is replaced if a new solution with better performance is found. The iterative process is repeated until a stop criterion is met. The algorithm returns the local transacted energy $x_{j,i,t}$ and the clearing price cp_t . The energy that is not transacted in the local market, i.e., $E_{i,t}^{\text{buy}}$ and $E_{j,t,s}^{\text{sell}}$, is sent to the aggregator for the next trading level.

III. CASE STUDY

This section presents the different LECs considered for the case study scenario. Subsection III.A introduces 5 LECs using the LEM model with centralized optimization, and subsection III.B describes 3 LECs using the double auction-based model with strategic bidding. Finally, subsection III.C presents 2 LECs composed of PV generation aiming to profit from LEMs instead of selling electricity to the grid at lower prices.

All LECs have the same aggregator. He is responsible for the trading in Lv1 and Lv2 of the multilevel electricity trading framework. The aggregator provides both models introduced in section II, and each community decides if it wishes to participate in a cooperative or a competitive local mode. Regarding Lv2, the aggregator runs a double auction-based model like the wholesale day-ahead market, using the unsatisfied demand and supply of each LEC to trade among communities. If, after Lv2 trading, there is still unsatisfied demand or supply and its amount is higher than 1 MWh, then the aggregator participates in the wholesale market, trying to buy or sell electricity at the best possible price. For the case study market simulation, the authors gathered data from the Iberian market operator repository [13], adding the aggregator bids.

A. LECs using LEM model with centralized optimization

Using the model presented in section II.A is possible to simulate different variants considering the resources available. The most complete scenario considers PV generation, home battery systems and two EVs per household. TABLE I presents the number of resources used to create the different LECs.

TABLE I. LECs USING LEM MODEL WITH CENTRALIZED OPTIMIZATION

LEC	Consumers	Prosumers	Batteries	EVs
1	39	61	43	200
2	39	61	43	0
3	39	61	0	200
4	39	61	0	0
5	39	61	43	100

LEC 1 is the most complete with 100 players (39 consumers and 61 prosumers), 43 players have home batteries installed and there are 200 EVs (two per player). LEC 2 has the same number of prosumers, consumers, and batteries, but there are no EVs. LEC 3 disregards home batteries. The simplest is LEC 4 without home batteries and EVs, and, finally, LEC 5 is the same as LEC 1 but considers one EV per player. Figure 3 presents the electricity export and import of all LECs in different periods.

Figure 3. LECs' electricity import and export

Analyzing Figure 3 is possible to see the different behavior of the different LECs. Most LECs import electricity during all time. Only LEC 4 has small amounts of electricity export during mid-day (when PV production is higher).

B. LECs using double auction-based model with strategic bidding

The model presented in Section II.B can be used to optimize the strategic bidding of a LEC with different configuration and tariffs. Table II shows the scenarios ran, comprising a LEC with 13 consumers, 42 prosumers with PV generation, and 6 CHP generators, having a total of 61 different players. Also, 29 prosumers have EVs.

TABLE II. LECs USING DOUBLE AUCTION-BASED MODEL WITH STRATEGIC BIDDING

LEC	Consumers	Prosumers	CHPs	Tariff
6	13	42	6	Plain
7	13	42	6	Bi-hourly
8	13	42	6	Tri-hourly

The main difference between these LECs is the retail tariff. This is an important parameter since it bounds the bid prices in the LEM. We consider two tariffs in the experiments, a plain tariff with 0.158 €/kWh for all periods, a bi-hourly tariff with 0.1023 €/kWh in off-peak periods (23h to 7h), and 0.1924 €/kWh in peak periods (8h to 22h), and a tri-hourly tariff with 0.1023 €/kWh in off-peak periods (23h to 7h), 0.1696 €/kWh in mid-peak periods (7h to 8h, 14h to 20h, and 22h), and 0.2358 in peak periods (11h to 13h, and 21h). Figure 4 shows the energy to be imported from the grid after simulating the three LECs.

Figure 4. Import and export electricity of the different LECs

Analyzing Figure 4, it is possible to see a large demand to be supplied in periods 18 to 21. Due to the characteristics of LECs, none can export electricity to the grid.

C. PV-based LECs

Using PV generations profiles, two different LECs are generated. These two LECs are very similar with small differences according to their solar electricity generation. Figure 5 presents the generation profiles of LECs-PV.

According to Figure 5, the peak PV generation is registered at mid-day. In this case both LECs-PV have the same objective, i.e., to sell electricity to other LECs, in wholesale market via an aggregator, or to the grid.

Figure 5. Electricity Generated by LECs

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the proposed framework. The presented section is divided into two subsections attending to the multi-level market participation.

A. Trading between LECs (Lv2)

Considering the import and export values of each LEC previously presented, a market between LECs can be executed. There are two LECs (LEC 9 and LEC 10) with available surplus. Figure 6 presents the outcomes of Lv2 trading.

Figure 6. Trading between LECs results

As it can be seen in Figure 6, there are only trading between periods 7 and 19, given that LECs 9 and 10 are PV-based. In period 15, the amount of traded energy is 180.49 kWh, and the market price was 0.053 €/kWh. In this period all generation was traded and only a small amount of demand (1.47 kWh) remained unsatisfied. As the overall Lv2 outcome, the total traded energy is 1019.42 kWh, and the mean price is 0.054 €/kWh.

Lv2 trading uses the double auction-based model, where each LEC submits bids with price and energy amount. The amount of energy is determined by the available surplus or needed demand. The bid price is determined between the interval of the feed-in tariff (as lower bound) and the minimum retailer tariff (as upper bound) of that hour for each LEC. This way, both buyers and sellers accomplish a win-to-win scenario and are keener to participate.

B. Wholesale trading (Lv3)

To participate in the wholesale market (Lv3), the aggregator must ensure a minimum of 1 MWh per trading period. Thus, given the unsatisfied demand and supply from the Lv2 trading (see Figure 6), the aggregator can only submit demand bids in periods 7, 18, 19, and 22-24. As in the previous level, prices are defined considering the feed-in tariff as lower bound, and the minimum retailer tariff of all LECs as upper bound. Figure 7 presents the Aggregator’s results in the wholesale market.

Figure 7. Aggregator’s results in the wholesale market

As it is possible to observe, the Aggregator bought all the required demand in the wholesale market. The bid prices submitted were always higher than the market price, ensuring the energy purchase. TABLE III presents a comparison of the results between a baseline and the multi-level framework proposed, and Figure 8 presents the same results categorized by LEC.

TABLE III. RESULTS COMPARISON

Scenario		Costs/Profits (€)	Total (€)
Baseline	Buy retailer	2250.70	18.68
	Sell retailer	-62.02	
Multi-level	Buy LECs Market	54.31	0.67
	Sell LECs Market	-54.31	
	Buy Wholesale	53.00	144.11
	Sell Wholesale	0.00	
	Buy retailer	1025.00	1025.44
	Sell retailer	-16.14	

Figure 8. Total amount of electricity traded considering each LEC

The baseline scenario considers each LEC running its LEM at Lv1, only, whereas the multi-level regards the proposed trading framework. Looking at the final costs, it is possible to see an aggregated cost reduction of 644.57 €.

V. CONCLUSION

The EU is promoting local balance and a self-sufficient community while lowering electricity costs by encouraging the development of LECs for electricity trading. LEMs facilitate electricity trading of DES, while encouraging the grid integration of RES. However, LEMs currently have low liquidity, and there is a greater demand than supply. Participation in the wholesale market, which would result in lower prices and more savings, is one potential solution to this problem. This work proposes a multilevel electricity trading simulation framework for LEC. The proposed framework considers 3 trading levels: trading within the LEC, trading between LECs, and wholesale trading. Results show the advantage of the proposed framework from the perspective of the LECs. Being able to trade in wholesale, allows for acquiring electricity at the lowest price. Future work includes testing and evaluating other LEM models to benefit LECs, making them active participants in electricity trading.

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